

THEORETICAL LEGAL ANALYSIS AND IMPORTANCE OF ENSURING GENDER EQUALITY IN INTERNATIONAL LAW

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11515034>

Promoting gender equality in international law is not just a matter of justice, it is essential to the protection of basic human rights and the promotion of global peace and prosperity. First, gender equality is a basic human right. International human rights law based on the Universal Declaration of Human Rights adopted on December 10, 1948¹ and the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW) adopted in 1979² recognizes that everyone has the same rights and freedoms. Ensuring gender equality in international law reaffirms this principle and creates a basis for holding countries accountable for protecting these rights. Promoting gender equality is essential for achieving sustainable development and economic growth. Studies have shown that countries with high gender equality have higher levels of economic efficiency and social development. By ensuring equal access to education, health and employment opportunities, international law helps unlock the full potential of all individuals, leading to more vibrant and prosperous societies.

Gender equality is also critical to peace and security on a global scale. Studies have shown that societies with greater gender equality experience less conflict and violence. By addressing the root causes of inequality and discrimination, such as unequal access to resources and decision-making power, international law can help prevent conflict and build more peaceful and stable societies. Also, ensuring gender equality in international law is important in solving pressing global problems such as poverty and health pandemics. Women and girls are often disproportionately affected by these problems and play a critical role in finding solutions. By encouraging their full participation and leadership, international law can help build stronger and more sustainable societies. Ensuring gender equality in international law is not only a matter of moral imperative; it is important for protecting human rights, promoting development, strengthening peace and security, and solving global problems. By working together to advance gender equality, we can create a fairer, more inclusive and prosperous world for all.

¹ Universal Declaration of Human Rights // <https://www.un.org/en/about-us/universal-declaration-of-human-rights>.

² The Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW) // <https://www.un.org/womenwatch/daw/cedaw/>.

Many international documents aimed at ensuring gender equality have been adopted, and it is appropriate to analyze them one by one and consider which areas are regulated:

The Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action, adopted at the Fourth World Conference on Women in 1995, is a comprehensive road map for achieving gender equality and expanding women's rights³. It covers areas such as women's rights, education, health, violence against women, women's participation in decision-making.

United Nations Security Council Resolution 1325 (UNSCR 1325) - Adopted in 2000, this resolution addresses the impact of armed conflict on women and calls for their participation in conflict prevention, peace negotiations and post-conflict recovery processes⁴. It also emphasizes the need to protect women and girls from gender-based violence during conflicts.

Istanbul Convention (Council of Europe Convention on preventing and combating violence against women and domestic violence) - this treaty, adopted by the Council of Europe in 2011, aims to prevent and combat violence against women and domestic violence aimed at combating⁵. It sets comprehensive measures to protect victims, bring perpetrators to justice and ensure gender equality.

Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) - Although not exclusively focused on gender equality, this 1989 treaty recognizes the rights of girls and boys to equal treatment and protection from discrimination. It includes provisions related to ensuring gender equality in education, health and protection from violence⁶.

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) - Although not legally binding, the SDGs, adopted by the United Nations General Assembly in 2015, include 5 goals to achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls by 2030. The BRMs provide a global framework for action on gender equality and women's empowerment⁷.

These are just a few examples of international legal instruments aimed at ensuring gender equality. There are many other regional and global agreements,

³ The Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action, adopted at the Fourth World Conference on Women in 1995 // <https://www.un.org/womenwatch/daw/beijing/pdf/BDPfA%20E.pdf>.

⁴ United Nations Security Council Resolution 1325 (UNSCR 1325) - Adopted in 2000 // https://peacemaker.un.org/sites/peacemaker.un.org/files/SC_ResolutionWomenPeaceSecurity_SRES1325%282000%29%28english_0.pdf.

⁵ Istanbul Convention (Council of Europe Convention on preventing and combating violence against women and domestic violence) // <https://www.coe.int/en/web/istanbul-convention>.

⁶ Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) // <https://www.ohchr.org/en/instruments-mechanisms/instruments/convention-rights-child>.

⁷ Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) // <https://sdgs.un.org/goals/goal5>.

declarations and conventions that contribute to women's rights and gender equality around the world. For example:

The Maputo Protocol, also known as the Protocol to the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights on Women's Rights in Africa, was adopted by the African Union in 2003. It addresses a variety of issues related to women's rights and gender equality, including political participation, education, health and economic empowerment⁸.

Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) - although this convention does not specifically focus on gender equality, this convention adopted in 2006 protects the rights of women and girls with disabilities, their access to opportunities and services there are rules aimed at ensuring equal use⁹.

Declaration on the Elimination of Violence against Women - Adopted by the United Nations General Assembly in 1993, this declaration recognizes violence against women as a violation of human rights and urges states to take measures to prevent and eliminate such violence. calls to see¹⁰. Although not legally binding, it provides important principles and guidelines for promoting gender equality and ending violence against women.

Convention on the Rights of Migrant Workers and Their Families - Although the convention does not specifically address gender equality, this 1990 treaty recognizes the vulnerabilities faced by migrant women and protects their rights in migration and gender issues. includes provisions aimed at promoting equality¹¹.

Convention on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP) - Adopted in 2007, this treaty recognizes the rights of indigenous women and their communities. It emphasizes the protection of indigenous women's rights, including participation in decision-making processes, education, health, and protection from discrimination and violence¹².

International Labor Organization (ILO) Conventions - Various ILO conventions address gender equality in the workplace, including the Equal Pay

⁸ Protocol to the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights on Women's Rights in Africa // <https://equalitynow.org/resource/twenty-years-of-the-maputo-protocol-where-are-we-now/>.

⁹ Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities // <https://www.ohchr.org/en/disabilities>.

¹⁰ Declaration on the Elimination of Violence against Women // <https://www.ohchr.org/en/instruments-mechanisms/instruments/declaration-elimination-violence-against-women>.

¹¹ Convention on the Rights of Migrant Workers and Their Families // <https://www.ohchr.org/en/instruments-mechanisms/instruments/international-convention-protection-rights-all-migrant-workers>.

¹² Convention on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP) // <https://www.ohchr.org/Documents/Issues/IPeoples/UNDRIPManualForNHRIs.doc>

Convention¹³, 1951 (No. 100) Labor and Occupation Convention - Equal pay for men and women for work of equal value requires payment¹⁴ and is dedicated to discrimination. 1958 (No. 111) aimed at eliminating discrimination in employment and occupation¹⁵.

Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court (ICC) – Adopted in 1998, the Rome Statute recognizes certain acts of gender-based violence, such as rape and sexual slavery, as crimes against humanity and war crimes. It provides a framework for holding perpetrators of such crimes accountable and seeking justice for victims, including women and girls¹⁶.

These international legal instruments form a comprehensive framework for promoting gender equality and women's rights at the global level. They provide guidance, standards and mechanisms for countries to meet their commitments to achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls.

Drawing on theoretical legal analysis, it emphasizes the interrelationship of gender equality with other fundamental principles of international law, such as non-discrimination, equality before the law and social justice. Gender discrimination violates the foundations of these principles. By mainstreaming gender equality into international legal instruments, it strengthens the commitment of states to address systemic barriers and injustices faced by women, girls and marginalized gender groups. This includes legal provisions prohibiting discrimination based on sex in all aspects of life, including education, employment, politics and access to justice. Promoting gender equality in international law is critical to combating entrenched cultural norms and practices that perpetuate gender-based violence and discrimination. Legal instruments such as the Declaration on the Elimination of Violence against Women and the Istanbul Convention provide a framework for states to recognize and combat gender-based violence as a violation of human rights and an obstacle to gender equality.

Importantly, the importance of gender equality in international law goes beyond its legal implications. It provides a framework for social change, challenging patriarchal systems and encouraging cultural change towards more inclusive and just societies. By recognizing the rights and dignity of all persons, regardless of gender, international law plays a crucial role in shaping the norms and values that underpin global solidarity and cooperation. Based on the

¹³ <https://www.ilo.org/global/standards/subjects-covered-by-international-labour-standards/equality-of-opportunity-and-treatment/lang--en/index.htm>.

¹⁴ https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---ed_norm/---declaration/documents/publication/wcms_decl_fs_84_en.pdf.

¹⁵ https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---ed_norm/---declaration/documents/publication/wcms_decl_fs_85_en.pdf.

¹⁶ Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court (ICC) // <https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/RS-Eng.pdf>.

analysis, it emphasizes the important role of gender equality in international law as a fundamental human right, a driver of development and peace, a basis for social change. By prioritizing gender equality in legal frameworks and practices, countries can contribute to a more just, inclusive and sustainable world for present and future generations.

The importance of gender equality in international law is highlighted by its role in the development of democracy and good governance. Gender-balanced representation in political decision-making processes ensures that diverse perspectives and experiences are taken into account, leading to more effective and inclusive policies. Legal frameworks guaranteeing women's participation in political and social life, such as quotas and positive measures, serve to eliminate structural barriers to women's empowerment and further strengthen democratic legitimacy¹⁷.

Furthermore, gender equality in international law is essential to promoting global health and well-being. Women and girls often face health problems such as reproductive health, maternal mortality and gender-based violence. Legal instruments such as the Convention on the Rights of the Child and the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities recognize the interconnectedness of gender with other identities and ensure that health policies and programs respond to diverse needs. .

emphasizes the multifaceted importance of gender equality in various fields, including human rights, democracy, health and environmental protection. By mainstreaming gender issues into legal frameworks and practices, countries can move towards a more just and sustainable world for all individuals, regardless of gender.

International law also extends to the field of conflict resolution and peace-building. Women and girls are not just passive victims of conflict; they are often powerful agents of change and peace are considered Legal frameworks such as¹⁸UN Security Council Resolution 1325 on Women, Peace and Security recognize the important role of women in conflict prevention, resolution and post-conflict recovery¹⁹. Ensuring the meaningful participation of women in peace processes not only expands the prospects for sustainable peace, but also eliminates the root causes of conflicts and promotes reconciliation. Gender equality is critical to the development of global justice and accountability. Women and girls are disproportionately affected by human rights violations, including sexual and

¹⁷<https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/gender-equality/>.

¹⁸<https://www.unwomen.org/en/what-we-do/peace-and-security>.

¹⁹<https://peacemaker.un.org/node/105>.

gender-based violence, human trafficking and exploitation. Legal mechanisms such as international tribunals and courts play an important role in bringing the perpetrators of these crimes to justice, justice and reparations for survivors ²⁰. In addition, legal frameworks that ensure impunity for gender-based violence and access to justice for all individuals, regardless of gender, are important to ensure the rule of law and promote human dignity.

In addition, gender equality in international law is important for strengthening global security and countering transnational threats such as terrorism and organized crime. While women and girls are often targeted by extremist groups and criminal networks, they are important actors in preventing and combating these threats. Legal frameworks that address the gender dimensions of security challenges and empower women as agents of prevention and resilience can help make security measures more effective and sustainable ²¹.

The importance of gender equality in international law is multi-faceted and wide-ranging, encompassing human rights, democracy, health, environmental protection, conflict resolution, peace-building, justice and security. By mainstreaming a gender perspective into legal frameworks and practice, countries can develop more inclusive, just and peaceful societies, resulting in increased collective well-being and dignity for all individuals, regardless of gender. Gender equality in international law is essential for the development of global cooperation and solidarity. In an interconnected world facing complex challenges such as climate change, pandemics and economic inequality, the full empowerment of all individuals, regardless of gender, is essential. Legal frameworks that promote gender equality facilitate cooperation and partnerships between states, organizations and civil society actors and enable more effective responses to common challenges and opportunities.

Ensuring gender equality is crucial in enhancing the rights and dignity of future generations. By establishing legal norms and standards that ensure gender equality, countries create the basis for sustainable progress and development that benefits current and future generations. Investing in gender equality today lays the foundation for a more just, inclusive and prosperous world for future generations. Gender equality in international law is essential to uphold the principles of universality and indivisibility of human rights. Gender-based discrimination and inequality not only violates the rights of individuals, but also undermines the integrity and credibility of the entire international

²⁰ <https://www.ohchr.org/en/development>.

²¹ <https://www.unwomen.org/en/what-we-do/peace-and-security>.

human rights framework. By prioritizing gender equality in legal frameworks and practices, States reaffirm their commitment to uphold the inherent dignity and equality of all human beings without discrimination.

international law is important for building resilience and adaptation to global crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic. Women and girls have been disproportionately affected by the socio-economic impacts of the pandemic, including job losses, increased caregiving responsibilities and increased risk of gender-based violence. Legal frameworks that prioritize gender-responsive and inclusive recovery efforts can help mitigate these disparities and restore more resilient, just, and inclusive societies.

The importance of gender equality in international law is aimed at shaping responses to emerging global challenges, advancing the development agenda and building resilience to crises. By mainstreaming a gender perspective into legal frameworks and practices, countries can develop more inclusive, just and sustainable societies where the rights and dignity of all individuals, regardless of gender, are upheld and protected.

In conclusion, the importance of gender equality in international law is aimed at encouraging innovation, solving emerging problems and promoting ethical governance in a rapidly changing world. By mainstreaming a gender perspective into legal frameworks and practices, countries can harness the transformative potential of gender equality to build stronger, more inclusive and sustainable societies for current and future generations.

The importance of gender equality is aimed at promoting global justice, human security and solidarity against complex and interconnected challenges. By mainstreaming a gender perspective into legal frameworks and practice, countries can move towards a peaceful, secure and stable world in which the rights and dignity of all persons, regardless of gender, are upheld and protected..

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11. Convention on the Rights of Migrant Workers and Their Families.
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